

sustainability report
2019

ginatricot

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Introduction

About Gina Tricot

Gina Tricot AB is a fashion company that sells clothing, jewellery, accessories and cosmetics for women. Gina Tricot was launched in Sweden in 1997 and now has stores in Sweden, Denmark, Finland, Norway and Germany.

An additional 23 European countries are served by e-commerce sales. Gina Tricot also sells products business to business. During 2019, the company had net sales of 2,006,000 SEK.

The company's head office is in Borås, Sweden, which is also the location of our central functions, including design, purchasing, IT, logistics, construction, business development and warehousing.

Gina Tricot are subject to the Swedish Annual Accounts Act provisions on non-financial information. We have chosen to report in accordance with the Global Reporting Initiative, GRI Standards, and the report is issued by our board. This is our seventh sustainability report prepared in accordance with GRI guidelines.

Highlights of our sustainability efforts in 2019

- Every single piece of our denims are produced in more sustainable materials
- 57% of our products were manufactured from more sustainable materials
- Replaced plastic shopping bags in stores with recycled paper bags
- Launch of Gina Tricot Mini and partnership with World Childhood Foundation
- Launch of RENT your party outfit

The year in review — A talk with our CEO

The Gina Tricot Sustainability team sat down with CEO Joachim Modigh, to discuss the year and what they found the most memorable, from a sustainability perspective.

- For me, I would say that 2019 was the year when climate issues really reached the masses. Many of us came to understand the very real consequences coming our way if we don't come together and take action to curb the global temperature rise.
Says Joachim Modigh.

- I agree, the massive fires in the Amazon, Australia and also the Greta effect really reached people all around the world. This, I think, has had the most impact for Gina Tricot's customers. We have received more questions than before and our internal commitment to climate issues is higher than ever. And with the Mistra Future Fashion report we know so much more about the fashion industry's impact.
Replies Rebecca Watkins.

- Also, many customers and staff have been very engaged in the issue of plastic and how we can minimise our use of plastics in our value chain. Here we have really listened and taken action; by signing Canopy's Pack4Good initiative, phasing out plastic bags in stores and minimising the use of plastic poly bags we set some quite important milestones this year. We're also now starting to phase out plastic bags from our online sales.
Says Emma Garrote.

- All these topics must be at the top of our minds for our future business. We need to make sure our 2028 goals are met, and together with new business models we will make the future more sustainable. Take RENT as an example – this is a typical way for Gina Tricot to work by challenging its customers and

trying new business models while focusing on environmental and economical sustainability.
Adds Joachim.

- This year we also offered our customers several other more sustainable projects like our upcycled collection which is locally produced in Borås from old customer returns and damaged goods, a tailor in-store to customise and repair torn denim, and selling our first Nordic Swan Eco label certified garment.
Says Rebecca.

- And the great thing is that we will continue with all of these start-up projects on a bigger scale in 2020. We will also continue our work to implement more sustainable fibres in our products – in 2019 we reached 57%!
Emma adds.

- For all our denim products we already reached 100% more sustainable materials this year!
Rebecca adds.

- And talking about denim, I naturally start to think about water. Water is an important resource in our production processes and supply chain, but also poses a big risk to our sector. In order to improve our understanding and response to water risks in the supply chain, we have started to use the WWF Water Risk Filter, which will enable us to identify the most critical issues to solve and make not only denim, but most of our water intense processes more resource efficient and less harmful for the environment.
Replies Joachim.

- I'm glad to see all the achievements from 2019, and I'm sure we will reach new heights next year, and continue to surprise and challenge customers within sustainability.
Ends Joachim.

Joachim Modigh, CEO

A better and more sustainable future for all

The world has 10 years to reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs are a collection of 17 global goals set by the UN General Assembly and adopted by all the UN Member states in 2015 to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all by 2030. They address the global challenges we face including those related to poverty, inequality, climate, environmental degradation, prosperity, and peace and justice.

The SDGs are a universal call to action, requiring everyone to join forces and collaborate in their role as a world citizen or business working in a global context. Each of the 17 goals is either directly or indirectly relevant to Gina Tricot. During 2019, we updated our analysis of the impact our business has on the areas highlighted in the 17 SDGs and found that we needed to add two more: No 13 Climate Action and No 6 Clean water and sanitation. These two SDGs are crucial for our business and we also have a huge impact here. All our pinpointed SDGs are part of our sustainability work and are leading the way towards better business practices.

"During 2019, we realised that we needed to add two more focus SDGs for our business; Climate Action and Clean Water and Sanitation. Climate and Water will be two of the keys within our sustainability work going forward. We need to do our best for future generations and we are committed to making a significant contribution to being part of the solution," says Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager.

Emma Garrote and Rebecca Watkins, sustainability team Gina Tricot

Our sustainability pledge

Gina Tricot is determined to be part of the solution, which is why we have formulated our own plan with clear targets for our organisation. During 2019 we analysed our previously set targets in depth, and made major updates. We have set more clear strategies on how to reach our targets, set new targets and strategies for water and climate as well as clarified the current targets.

"This year we updated our commitment for a more sustainable business by 2028. We added some strategies and more details on how to reach our goals. The SDGs are a great support here, and the most vital one is no 17 – Partnerships for the goals!"

says Emma Garrote, Production and Sustainability Manager.

By 2028, we will only provide:

- **Products made of materials that are more environmentally sustainable.**
We currently define a sustainable material as being a recycled, organic or innovative new material within this area.
- **Products produced in a more sustainable manner.**
The entire supply chain from fibre to finished product will be sustainable, transparent, and third-party or internally audited.
- **Products that are designed for the circular economy,** aimed at being reused and in the end recycled.
- **Products that are transported in a sustainable manner** with less carbon emissions and using fossil free fuel alternatives.
- **Products that are sold in a sustainable channel.**
Stores and online channels that have sustainable interiors, packaging, electricity and waste control.

On the path to 2028

For Gina Tricot our future success within sustainability will depend on close cooperation with our partners, both suppliers and experts. We must also support and remain involved in scientific research and product development.

Our efforts to use more environmentally sustainable materials require that we constantly stay up-to-date on new research and developments in the field.

We will also put a lot of effort into the environmental impact of production over the coming years, including water use, energy use and type, as well as the use of chemicals in production. This is in order to minimise the environmental impact of our production processes.

We want to be part of making the fashion industry more sustainable by setting tough goals and pursuing dedicated efforts that permeate our entire organisation. It is essential, though, that everyone in the fashion industry embraces the circular economy and makes a meaningful contribution.

Our efforts towards our 2028 targets are guided by the following strategies

PEOPLE

- Production strategy
- Marketing strategy
- Employment strategy
- Women's empowerment strategy

PRODUCT

- Product strategy
- Material strategy

PLANET

- Transportation strategy
- Packaging material strategy
- Climate and water strategy
- Construction and expansion strategy

Stakeholder engagement

In our ongoing dialogue with stakeholders, these stakeholders are either actively selected by us when needed to discuss particular issues, or we are the ones responding to questions from stakeholders.

Our most important stakeholders are our customers, both our existing customers and potential new ones. We engage with our customers on a daily basis, both face-to-face in our stores, and through our online platform and in our social media channels.

The table below presents our key stakeholders, how we communicate with them, the topics they consider to be most important and how we address them.

STAKEHOLDER	COMMUNICATION	KEY SUSTAINABILITY TOPICS	LINK TO OUR MATERIAL TOPICS (PAGE 47)
OWNERS AND BOARD OF DIRECTORS	Meetings e.g. Board meetings, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Health and safety in production and for employees. Human Rights. Quality and environmental impact of products. Transports.	Social conditions in our supply chain. Occupational health and safety. Product liability. Materials. Energy and emissions.
EMPLOYEES	Continuous discussions through surveys, meetings, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Sustainable materials. Human rights. Animal welfare. Health and safety in production. Environmental impact of production.	Materials. Social conditions in our supply chain. Animal welfare issues. Environmental impact of suppliers.
STUDENTS (through Inquiries and comments, mainly through social media)	Lectures, projects, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Health and safety in production. Climate impact. Circular Economy. Animal welfare. Sustainable materials.	Social conditions in our supply chain. Environmental impact of suppliers. Energy and emissions. Animal welfare issues. Materials.
EXPERTS/RESEARCHERS	Ongoing dialogue through network meetings, projects, collaborations, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Transparency. Circular economy. Environmental impact of production. Climate impact. Product lifespan.	Environmental impact of suppliers. Product liability. Energy and emissions. Materials.
CUSTOMERS	Dialogue on a daily basis through various channels like customer service, stores, online and social media, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Health and safety in production. Transport. Sustainable materials. Animal welfare. Product quality.	Social conditions in our supply chain. Energy and emissions. Materials. Animal welfare issues. Product liability.
SUPPLIERS	Regular visits to our suppliers, supplier evaluation, stakeholder dialogue 2018	Environmental impact in production. Sustainable materials, Climate impact. Empowerment of women.	Environmental impact of suppliers. Materials. Energy and emissions. Gender equality.
OTHERS (governments, media, NGOs)	Projects, collaboration forum, interviews, 2018 stakeholder engagement	Health and safety in production. Equality. Environmental impact of production. Fair pay. Children's rights.	Social conditions in our supply chain. Energy and emissions. Environmental impact of suppliers. Social conditions in our supply chain.

Anna Lidström - An expert's view on a sustainable fashion industry

We met our former Gina Tricot colleague Anna Lidström for a chat regarding sustainability and the fashion industry. Anna is a fashion designer, influencer and PhD student in sustainable fashion at the Swedish School of Textiles. She is currently Creative Director at Re:Textile.

What does sustainability mean to you?

It's about achieving an environmental, social and economic balance, and meeting the needs of today without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs and aspirations. It's about supporting all life on the planet, not only human life.

Which sustainability issues are most important to you?

One important issue to me is the topic of reducing the use of virgin raw materials globally – humans use more resources than the earth is capable of restoring. I'm also interested in biodiversity connected to the Sustainable Development Goals 14 and 15, which address ecosystems in the oceans and on land. This is also the theme for the WIN Gothenburg Sustainability Award 2020 (a non-profit association financed by the City of Gothenburg, Region Västra Götaland and eleven other member organisations and companies).

I'm part of the jury, and will work with the topic over the next year. Another environmental issue that really frightens me, and sometimes keeps me up at night, is the effect of Global warming.

What would you say are the main challenges that face the fashion industry?

From my research perspective, my main interest lies in the context of redesigning, remaking and reconstructing fashion. Redesigning is about giving something a new lease of life, adding value, through design. I'm really interested in the repurposing of lower-valued clothes, post- or pre-consumer waste, and how I, as a designer, can transform them into a new fashionable product with a fresh value. Redesign can vary according to how much the garment is changed, from adding minor design details such as a decorative trim, to changes to the garment's silhouette such as adding a frill, to the complete transformation of the garment's original purpose such as changing a dress into a bag.

I strongly believe in the power of leftover fabrics, and the development of alternative design methods and business models in relation to that. Another important aspect of redesigning is that it reduces the usage of virgin fibres, since it enables companies to make more money and more designs with what's already been produced. I believe that there is great potential within this field. And scalability when working with redesign is important, especially if it's surplus production that feeds into this 'alternative loop' of redesign production.

Another important aspect for the fashion industry to consider is to develop alternatives to buying new clothes, like the development of renting and mending services.

Yet another important topic is to cut down the usage of conventional virgin fibres. I wish companies could join forces with the scientists and push for the development of fibre recycling – making old garments into textile material. Today less

than 1% of recycled material on the world market comes from recycled clothes fibres, the rest is from other sources. Here, redesign could also coexist as a business model.

In addition, I believe that we will have a huge discussion concerning the downsides of online shopping, such as transportation, discarded returns, and over consumption.

What do you think about Gina Tricot?

It's really interesting that Gina Tricot's customers are able to rent 'party outfits', I think that inspires others to follow suit. I'm interested to see the response from such a young target group as well. I'm also very glad, and proud, of the redesign collaboration within the setting of our 'micro factory' between Re:Textile, XV Production and Gina Tricot in the autumn of 2019.

What do you think we could improve?

I think this is something that every fashion brand is struggling with at the moment – how to raise the quality, make smaller quantities, and sell at a slightly higher price. Teaching customers, step by step that fashion has a value, and needs to cost more. And I would like to see Gina's renting and redesigning projects scaled up. More customers need to get hold of those good alternatives and initiatives instead of always buying new clothes.

Give us your top 3 things that we should focus on during 2020 to be a positive force.

Gina Tricot should continue to develop its alternative business models -- remake and rent. And Gina Tricot should work even more on being transparent, especially regarding production and supply chains. I believe more and more customers will demand that, especially in the era of the fast growing global movement Fashion Revolution. I would also love to see more pioneer collaborations on redesign together with Re:Textile and XV Production.

Anna Lidström, Creative Director at Re:Textile

Materiality analysis

The materiality analysis from 2015 included in-depth interviews with stakeholders and a workshop with our management and relevant senior executives. Minor updates were carried out in 2016 and 2017 from an impact perspective.

An overall assessment of the environmental, social and economic impact of Gina Tricot via its business was factored into the final prioritisation of aspects reported. We also annually summarise the issues that have come up in the ongoing dialogue we have with our stakeholders.

Our materiality analysis resulted in a list of our most material topics, see sustainability management table on page 47. These are the aspects that serve as the core of our sustainability report even during 2019.

In an analysis of our level of impact rate for the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, we found that our operations to some extent touch on all these goals, either directly or indirectly. During 2019

we added two more as our focus SDGs. On page 6, you can read about the six goals in which we can make the biggest difference.

In the sustainability management table on page 47, we linked our efforts to reduce negative impact to each SDG and our material topics.

People

People are at the heart of everything we do, and we want to have a positive impact on everyone who works with us. From the farmers who grow our cotton to the sales staff in our stores.

Transparent supply chain

"Social sustainability is about identifying and managing business impacts, both positive and negative, on people. The quality of a company's relationships and engagement with its stakeholders is critical. Directly or indirectly, companies affect what happens to employees, workers in the value chain, customers and local communities, and it is important to manage impacts proactively." – UN Global Compact ¹

¹ Social Sustainability, United Nations Global Compact

Our production strategy is well rooted in the company and it strives to minimise the number of suppliers in order to build strong relations with our selected key business partners. We know that via partnerships and strong business relations we can have a stronger impact, especially in the field of sustainability. One of the challenges facing the textile industry is achieving a higher level of transparency from suppliers and production units. Our customers care about all aspects of sustainability, and of course we want to be able to give them full information on product origin. For the last couple of years, Gina Tricot has put a great deal of effort into documenting our sup-

ply chain with our suppliers' suppliers. This year, we have been able to put even more focus on suppliers further down the supply chain. In total, we completed 17 site visits to our suppliers' suppliers in our production countries in 2019.

During 2019, as part of our efforts towards increased transparency, we started to publish information on our suppliers and production units for all our products. For more information, please visit www.ginatricot.com

We are committed and dedicated to building full transparency throughout our entire supply chain down to raw material level.

- Today we have full transparency in our supply chain from sewing unit down to fabric producer. Some fibre producers are also selected by Gina Tricot.
- We're currently mapping our cotton, viscose and leather supply chains.
- We collaborate with organisations such as CanopyStyle to help us better understand the complex nature of our supply chains, while providing us with responsible sourcing assurance.
- We are nominating many suppliers' suppliers such as labels, packaging and thread suppliers to maintain a better control.

Nordictex Tekstil, Istanbul Turkey

Our production — 2019

Supplier evaluation

Annual supplier evaluations are a very important part of Gina Tricot's sustainability efforts. We rely on the results to identify key business partners and consolidate our orders. The evaluation has three components, each affecting the final score according to the following distribution: buying and design, sustainability and logistics.

There is a possible maximum score, where 90 % fulfilment equals Diamond status, 80 % equals Gold status, 70 % equals Silver status and 60 % equals Bronze status.

We request that all suppliers with Silver or Bronze status submit an action plan for improvement in particular areas and we carefully monitor their progress. Our intention is to help and support suppliers to be able to reach a higher evaluation level, but it's important that our suppliers share our vision for improvement.

"We believe in local presence and personal supplier visits and seeing production with our own eyes to make sure working environments for employees live up to our standards. Our local presence in production countries is the key to our social sustainability work."

Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager.

■ Gina Tricot purchasing markets based on purchasing value. External brands are not included.

■ Local presence

Fakir Fashions Ltd, Dhaka Bangladesh

Fair production

In our biggest production markets, Turkey, Bangladesh and China, we have dedicated sustainability staff working daily in close collaboration with our suppliers. This makes us able to go deeper into the supply chain, make visits further down the chain and take quicker actions on findings made. During 2019, we started to visit our suppliers' suppliers in China, as well as continued visits in Bangladesh and Turkey. This is an ongoing job, and we will continue to visit and work towards a better production chain further down the supply chain as it is our responsibility to make sure that each worker in our supply chain is respected, feels safe and is financially secure. Our ways of doing this include:

- Regular third-party audits by amfori BSCI to set the base line and minimum requirements
- Regular Gina Tricot audits to make sure our own standards are met. Both announced and unannounced visits are performed
- Collaboration with stakeholders for long-lasting improvements in the supply chain within different areas like women's rights and workplace safety

Supplier status	2016	2017	2018	2019
Number of suppliers	73	57	61	58
Number of production units	144	115	103	116
Number of amfori inspections completed	74	69	79	71
Number of follow-up visits by Gina Tricot	131	261	305	194

number excluding external brands

amfori BSCI

Since 2008 we have been a member of amfori BSCI (previously known as BSCI, Business Social Compliance Initiative), one of the world's largest organisations for ensuring systematic, independent supply chain auditing. amfori BSCI is based on 13 principles covering, among others, fair remuneration, decent working hours and discrimination. Through amfori BSCI, our suppliers are regularly audited and remediation plans are established to help them improve. Find more info about amfori at amfori.org.

The Accord on fire and building safety in Bangladesh (the Accord)

Since 2013 we have been a member of the Accord. The Accord provides factory inspections, monitors remediation, safety training and resolves safety complaints. Through the Accord, committed, together with all our suppliers in Bangladesh, to improving the building, fire and electrical safety in the factories. We have 10 factories in Bangladesh that are part of the Accord, meaning 100% of our suppliers in Bangladesh. In total these factories had 63 follow-up inspections during 2019, with a total progress rate of 89%. Key focuses for the suppliers have been to install fire hydrants, sprinklers and fire alarm systems.

Workplace accident at a Bangladeshi supplier

In late 2019, a tragic workplace accident occurred at one of our suppliers in Bangladesh. A worker died from serious head injuries after a fall on a trolley. Within the next working week our local- and head office visited the supplier to thoroughly go through the accident, cause and measures to be taken. The investigation showed that reasonable safety routines were in place and had been followed. However, new routines for loading and working with trollies were suggested from our side. Our supplier paid the worker's family the regulatory insurance amount as well as an extra payment.

Fire in a weaving unit in Bangladesh

In late 2019, our denim supplier's weaving unit in Bangladesh suffered a fire caused by an overheated machine in the finishing stage. The factory's sprinkler system extinguished the fire quickly. No worker was injured, and there was no major damage to the building.

Fair remuneration

Workers throughout the supply chain are entitled to a wage, excluding overtime, that meets all the basic needs for themselves and their family. For many people working around the world fair remuneration is unfortunately not a given. In order to improve, we first need to measure and get precise information about the situation.

According to our Code of Conduct and local legislation, our suppliers are obliged to pay at least the country's statutory minimum wage to their employees. However, the problem is that minimum wage is rarely enough to cover a worker's basic needs. We are aware of the issues and are trying to be a positive influence, together with amfori and our local representatives, to improve the situation and create a shift in the industry.

Gina Tricot started to measure wages at our suppliers during 2018. We completed the wage evaluation in Bangladesh, Turkey, India and Pakistan during 2019. In 2020, our goal is to complete the work for all our suppliers in China. We will go into more depth with these figures and results as well as look at how we can make a positive impact upon wages paid.

Through amfori, Gina Tricot is also monitoring the wages paid to employees who manufacture our garments at amfori audited suppliers.

Country	Average wage	Comparison to legal min wage
Bangladesh	9,041 BDT (based on 21,298 workers)	+13%
India	10,164 INR (based on 877 workers)	+27%
Pakistan	16,926 PK (based on 2,371 workers)	+13%
Turkey	2,150 TL (incl.AGI) (based on 4,500 workers)	+5%

Ordu Maydenim, Ordu Turkey

Giga tekstil san ve Dış tic Ltd şti, Istanbul Turkey

Rights of employment

Turkey is Gina Tricot's biggest production market. As a result of the ongoing Syrian civil war, more than 3.2 million refugees have fled the country to Turkey looking for a safer life and naturally also looking for work. This is an opportunity for the refugees to be able to get a job, steady income and possibility to support their family's needs and dreams. However, exposed workers often risk uncertain terms of employment. Gina Tricot must ensure that all Syrian refugees working in production in Turkey have valid working permits. This is a problem within the industry, but we believe that a close relationship with our suppliers as well as frequent visits helps us to manage this issue. During our frequent supplier visits, we always check that all workers have valid work permits. This helps ensure that their rights are protected.

Cases of missing working permits

In late 2019, we found two suppliers' suppliers which had Syrian refugees working without working permits. We immediately met the suppliers, informed them about our finding and urged them to arrange working permits for the workers through the NGO United Works. Before the end of the year, the workers had the correct working permits. Unfortunately, one of the suppliers' suppliers went bankrupt, and the workers needed to seek a job elsewhere. At the other suppliers' supplier, the workers kept their jobs but are now able to work legally with the correct working permits.

Workers right to influence

We consider a good employment to be one where the workers can be heard and have an opportunity to change the workplace for the better.

Many of our suppliers have worker committees. In these committees elected workers get to represent the workforce and lead the change through democratic elections. We also have one Turkish supplier, Maydenim, leading the way, which will hopefully inspire other suppliers to sign an agreement with the Turkish trade union Teksif. The agreement between Maydenim and Teksif is important as it means that the union can now negotiate and bargain collectively.

Empowering women

May 2019 marked the 100-year anniversary of women getting the right to vote in Sweden. In the past 100 years we have seen big accomplishments worldwide in the field of gender equality, but unfortunately gender inequality is still prevalent in every society. We still have a long way to go before reaching the UN's Sustainable Development Goal of Gender equality.

"Achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls is close to the heart of those who work at Gina Tricot. There are 97% women in our organisation and women make up the majority of employees in our value chain. Our business aims to allow all women to be the best version of themselves."
- Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager

Gina Tricot aims to allow not only our customers and staff - but also women in our supply chain, to be able to be that best version of themselves. Gina Tricot strives to contribute to a fair, humane, inclusive, equal and inspiring workplace. This might sound simple and easy, but in many of the countries we operate in, legislation around these issues is lacking or not implemented correctly. But even more of a problem is that structures and cultures complicate and sometimes impede the improvements to be made.

As a part of the amfori BSCI, we are joining forces with over 2,000 other brands and engaging with not only suppliers, but with governments to push the legislation in the right direction. By ensuring safe working conditions and available health services, suppliers will also gain from reduced sick-leave and more committed staff.

UN Women Sweden's top focus areas for Gina Tricot.

- Invest in women's health
- Ensure safe working conditions
- Get women into employment throughout the value chain

Gender equality target 2028

Use external stakeholders to inform and encourage gender-equal production at all our first-tier suppliers. Map the number of women in managerial positions in all first-tier suppliers and advocate female leaders.

"Achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls is close to the heart of those who work at Gina Tricot."

Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager

From the Aéryne collection for UN Women

Women in production

One main topic when talking with factory owners and producers around the world is how they work with and encourage women in management positions.

This year we have also started to conduct audits with our biggest suppliers to measure the number of women in managerial positions, and we have conducted audits with 100% of our factories in Bangladesh. The goal is to work proactively to increase the number of female managers in production countries by closely monitoring and increasing the value of this figure.

As a global standard Gina Tricot only works with suppliers and companies that respect human rights and women's rights. All suppliers to Gina Tricot must sign our General Agreement that stands behind amfori BSCI's demands for fair remuneration and good working conditions for everyone, regardless of gender.

The number of women working in the textile industry is huge, and in Bangladesh alone over 80% of the country's 4 million readymade garment workers are female. To expand economic growth, promote social development and enhance business performance in a country, one key is to involve women in full and productive employment. We are proud to support the empowerment of women in the supply chain. When women get a job and salary, they also get a stronger voice and have improved power to make their own decisions.

20% of our suppliers in Bangladesh are enrolled in UNICEF's programme Mothers@work. This is a national initiative to support maternity rights and protect breast feeding among working mothers in the garment industry. In total 3,150 female workers from our suppliers are engaged.

Through Mothers@Work, female employees in Bangladesh are given increased knowledge about health, including sexual and reproductive health and pre- and postnatal health. Within this project seven minimum standards are to be worked with to ensure working women's rights:

1. No heavy work during pregnancy
2. Maternity leave, recommended 6 months
3. Cash and medical benefits in relation to pregnancy and childbirth
4. Reservation of position for women on maternity leave
5. Provision of breastfeeding space at work
6. Provision of 2 breastfeeding breaks
7. Provision of childcare at factory campus

The enrolled factories that work in line with the project are investing in women's health, securing equal opportunities for both women and men. This will have a positive effect, not only for the factory itself but also for society. Other expected benefits include a reduction in absence and staff turnover which will improve productivity and directly contribute to decent work and economic growth.

UN Women Sweden and Gina Tricot

In July 2010, UN Women was created – UN Women is the United Nations entity dedicated to gender equality and the empowerment of women. A global champion for women and girls, UN Women was established to accelerate progress on meeting their needs worldwide. UN Women works for the elimination of discrimination against women and girls, the empowerment of women, and the achievement of equality between women and men as partners and beneficiaries of development, human rights, humanitarian action and peace and security.

We have been supporting UN Women since 2017. Together with local partners, UN Women works to stop female genital mutilation, one of the worst forms of violation against young girls and women. Other programmes include stopping child marriages, ensuring that girls are given the same right to education, giving women access to trauma-treatment for those who have been subjected to rape in conflict and war situations, ensuring that women take part in peace negotiations, and em-

powering them to take a more active part in political decisions and society. UN Women also addresses the endemic existence of gender-based violence.

UN Women Sweden supports the mission of UN Women through their public awareness initiatives about UN Women and global women's issues, and fundraising efforts to support UN Women programmes for the empowerment of women worldwide.

On International Women's Day 2019, Gina Tricot hosted the second Power Girl Award Gala. The event was a closed event held for our fantastic customers. We wanted to praise people who dare to influence the world in a positive way.

During the gala we handed over 1,655 911 SEK to UN Women Sweden, which includes 100% of the income from the ticket sales and garment sales at the gala, but biggest part of the donation comes from One Bag Habit initiative.

Other activities in collaboration with UN Women Sweden during the year include the Gina Tricot X Aéryne collection, a collection made from leftover fabrics, where 10% of the sales price of the entire collection was donated to UN women Sweden.

During orange payday, on 25th of November, Gina Tricot held a sample sale and the income was donated to UN Women Sweden.

Dress for Success Stockholm x Gina Tricot

In spring 2019, Gina Tricot teamed up with Dress for Success Stockholm.

Dress for Success's mission is to empower women to achieve economic independence by providing a network of support, professional attire and the development tools to help women thrive in work and in life.

"Our vision is a world where women do not live in poverty; are treated with dignity and respect; and are strengthening their families and shaping their communities."

Angelique de la Vega, Founder, Dress for Success Stockholm

Dress for Success is an international non-profit organisation that since 1997 has expanded to more than 150 cities and 30 countries around the world, and has helped more than one million women work towards economic self-sufficiency.

This year, Gina Tricot contributed with clothes and gift cards and funds for the women in the programme, and we also arranged and participated in a workshop focusing on job interview techniques.

The workshop was held in Gina Tricot's flagship store at Götgatan in Stockholm, together with 40 specially invited women from the Dress for Success Stockholm network. The evening was filled with events and tips on how to have a successful job interview and a good CV.

"For Gina Tricot, it's very important to not only contribute with funds, we also want to contribute our expertise and knowledge. We know that by taking small steps we can make a big change in someone's life"

Helen Kry, HR Director

One woman was also offered a paid internship in one of the Gina Tricot stores.

Gina Tricot women worldwide

We sat down with some of our high-achieving female colleagues worldwide to discuss women's empowerment in the supply chain, from a Chinese and Turkish perspective.

Elaine Chai is our Product Manager at our Chinese office, located in Shanghai. She joined Gina Tricot in 2013, and since 2018 she has been leading the work at the office.

Elaine, what would you estimate the number of women in leading positions in our supply chain to be?

I would say that women make up the majority of the leading positions, 80% or more.

Wow, that's impressive – we can learn from that in many of our other production countries. If we look at challenges for these women, what would you say they are?

Most female workers lack higher education. Luckily there are not so many challenges regarding violations of women, and things have improved a lot over the last 10 years. We see women being more financially independent and not being so dependent on their families, and with that also comes more freedom and the right to make your own decisions.

Interesting. What would you say is the biggest challenge for Gina Tricot for the future, in order to make sure the UN SDG on Gender Equality is met?

I believe in information and the power of knowledge. We would need to inform suppliers more about the importance of

gender equality. There are still some cultural hurdles, but many realise the importance of equality. I think women need financial independence first, then increased education and they also need to become more visionary. If women are empowered today, the future generation of women will be too!

Elaine Chai, Product Manager in Shanghai

Pinar Kursun is our CSR expert in Turkey, and she has been working in depth with our Turkish suppliers for the past 3 years.

Pinar, what would you estimate the number of women in leading positions in our supply chain to be?

I would say we still have a long way to go here in Turkey, around 40-50% of workers in production are women, but in managerial positions the figure is 10% maximum.

Okay, there is definitely room for improvement here! If we look at the challenges for these women, what would you say they are?

Most female workers work a lot of overtime, which naturally affects their private life and family. There is also a big problem with day-care solutions in Turkey, unfortunately leading to many mothers not going back to work after having children. They are also facing discrimination; newly married women are disadvantaged in the recruitment process and it is also quite common that their families stop them from working.

That's some serious discrimination! Have there been any improvements?

Some, especially thanks to brands pushing equality questions.

What would you say is the biggest challenge for Gina Tricot for the future, in order to make sure the UN SDG on Gender Equality is met?

No doubt cultural barriers. Some families still stop their women from working, or take the young girls' salaries for the family income, leaving them with nothing. From Gina Tricot's side I would say that we need to inform more! As this is mainly a

cultural issue, we need to inform families, company owners and supervisors, all through the supply chain. I also believe we should gather more information in the supply chain about the situation, and based on this set higher demands. We all benefit from stronger, more independent women.

Pinar Kursun, CSR expert in Turkey

Our impact on children

Gina Tricot has an impact on children through our business in many ways, either directly or indirectly. Examples of this include selling children's wear, being the employer of their parents and collaborating with factories where parents work.

We have a big responsibility due to our impact on children's lives and their future and want what's in the best interests of children. We believe that all children should be able to grow up in a clean and safe environment, and be protected from violence and exploitation and have the possibility to thrive and learn.

We are aware of the impact our marketing has on children and youth. We are careful when advertising our products and have chosen a playful approach in all our ways of communicating about children's wear. The products are unisex and we are taking clear stands against gender stereotyping as well as the sexualisation of children.

In our Code of Conduct from amfori BSCI, we have zero tolerance for child labour, and strict restrictions for young workers' safety and appropriate work and hours. We also recognise the part we play in the local communities where we produce. We know that many families move to urban areas in order to have an income, meaning that children are often left behind with

other caregivers than their parents because of the lack of day-care in the cities. This often leads to a lack of education and daily contact with their parents.

Together with our partners we strive to impact on each child's life in a positive way. Through funding the social investments such as The United Nations Children's Fund, UNICEF and World Childhood Foundation we support the great work they are doing.

UNICEF's top focus areas for Gina Tricot:

- Require fair and family friendly working conditions
- Work with local authorities and organisations to improve living standards for families
- Find working business models for responsible and sustainable consumption, to ensure coming generation's needs.

UNICEF and Gina Tricot

UNICEF works to save children's rights, protect the rights of every child, help them fulfil their potential and improve the lives of children and their families. Gina Tricot has been a close collaborator of UNICEF in Bangladesh since 2009, and this continued during 2019. An estimated 2.23 million people live in slums across the country. For children living in slum areas in Bangladesh, life is difficult and often dangerous, with high rates of school dropout, child marriage, child labour and abuse. Without the meaningful inclusion of women, girls and communities in addressing the behaviour and norms, the desire and need for change is hindered or stalled.

The current UNICEF programme funded by Gina Tricot has been running from 2016 up until the end of 2019, with high aims – to transform behaviours and social norms in slum communities. The goal of the programme is to give 150,000 children and caregivers in targeted urban areas improved access to health, nutrition, water and sanitation and educational services, and to feel more protected and empowered to participate meaningfully in decisions that affect their lives. The programme reaches women, family members and adolescent girls at a local level. With our support, other donors and UNICEF's regular resources during 2017-2019, UNICEF has been able to reach more than 145,000 children between 0 and 18 years old and caregivers in selected poor urban communities of Dhaka North and Gazipur city corporations.

Achievement through UNICEF's trainings, financial and technical support are, among many others:

Health

- 90,200 infants were immunised
- 1,000 girls received counselling on menstrual hygiene management
- 2,000 children were covered by birth registration

Nutrition

- 1,200 children were screened and treated for severe and acute malnutrition

Water and sanitation

- 6,800 children and their parents/caregivers were given access to safely managed sanitation facilities
- 5,200 children and their parents/caregivers increased their awareness on the benefits of hand washing, the use of safe water and clean toilets
- 300 children and their parents/caregivers were given access to safe water and sanitation through WASH Blocks

Educational services

- 315 children, benefitted from community-based day-care centres
- Early learning centres for 2,000 children were established
- 4,110 out of school children are receiving basic education in ability-based learning centres

Children's rights and business programme

20% of our suppliers in Bangladesh are also part of the Children's rights and business programme – Better Business for Children, a programme initiated by UNICEF.

Our suppliers participating in the project commit to the following:

- Develop and implement industry-leading maternity rights policies & practices and increase the number of workers availing these benefits.
- Improve the health and nutritional status of workers, with a specific focus on female workers, and their children through targeted and effective evidence-based interventions.
- Develop and implement industry-leading water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) policies and practices.
- Introduce industry-leading policies and practices that support lactating women workers.

GinaTricot x World Childhood Foundation

CHILDHOOD

WORLD CHILDHOOD FOUNDATION

FOUNDED BY H.M. QUEEN SILVIA OF SWEDEN

In the spring of 2019, Gina Tricot launched a brand-new concept called Gina Tricot Mini. The idea originates from one of our employees, Johanna Hernström.

"The idea came to me when my daughter was born, and I felt such a strong bond between us. I have always been impressed and inspired by the women in my life and when I became a mother myself I realised how powerful women and mothers really are. It inspired me to create a matching collection for mums and their minis as a symbol for the strong bond between a mother and her child"

Johanna Hernström, Project Manager Creative

It's a unisex concept from ages 6 months up to 7 years. The majority of the collection is made from more sustainable materials. Each collection has around 5 uniquely selected pieces where 10% of the sales price is donated to Childhood.

World Childhood Foundation is a children's rights organization that works to prevent violence and sexual abuse of children. One in five children in Sweden is the victim of sexual abuse in their childhood. Terrible figures — but we still talk so little about it. At Childhood, we want to break this silence, because we know that violence and abuse of children can be prevented.

Childhood was founded in 1999 by H. M. Queen Silvia of Sweden. Our efforts are based on the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and we have no religious or political affiliation. Our vision is to ensure that no children find themselves in a violent and risky living environment, and for all children to have a safe and loving childhood, free from violence and sexual abuse. Childhood receives no government support but finances its operations solely through voluntary contributions.

Care for colleagues

Interview with our HR and Talent Management Director Heléne Kry

What does work-life balance mean to you?

Work-life balance is important to me, and our employees have the freedom to plan and deliver their work. I believe autonomy and transparency are significant for sustainable careers.

How do you work to create this balance for the employees?

We encourage our employees to prioritise their own work tasks. However, to truly enable employee self-management, it is important that we as an employer create the right prerequisites. For example, we have provided leadership training for managers and have during the year implemented a new system called Winningtemp at head office, which measures employee contentment and wellbeing every other month.

This is one example of our efforts to create a better psychosocial work environment, as the system will give a fast and continuous overview of both acute problems and long-term development in order to reduce stress and increase job satisfaction.

We believe that all employees are guided by our values when making their daily decisions. For us it's important that our employees feel proud to be a part of our journey and that we

share the same passion. We measure this using an Employee Net Promoter Score (ENPS), and at the end of 2019 our ENPS was (KPI) and our aim is to increase it to (KPI).

We also believe in preventing both physical and psychological health issues, through offering our wellness grant for employees in Sweden. We also encourage our employees to exercise and focus on their health.

It's been a tough year. How did you handle this?

We started with a company-wide saving programme where we were forced to do a lot of cost cutting including laying off employees at head office, and we were also forced to cut hours in our stores. These changes have resulted in an increased workload for some of our employees and as a consequence increased stress and increased sick leave.

Because of this, we have been extra conscious and trained our managers to look out for any signs of stress or mental illness from an early stage. This has enabled us to offer pre-talks and pre-support with a psychologist or therapist through our company healthcare programme. We have already seen a good result from this preventative work.

How do you work with sustainable careers?

We believe in our employees and we know they are the key to our success. Diversity is an important factor when recruiting

and developing our employees. We consider diversity as an asset to our company because this leads to a dynamic workplace. The most important thing is to get the right talents into the company who share the values of Gina Tricot. We do this by showing them what we offer and making sure that they are able to build a career within the company.

This year we have worked with our Employee value proposition (EVP) to showcase examples of internal careers to help attract the right talents and show what we as a company can offer. We make it possible for our employees to create a career within the company, either through promotions or broadening their skills by working in a different department. In 2019, we filled 67 posts using talent from within the company.

What is your view on discrimination?

Gina Tricot rejects all forms of discrimination regarding gender, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation or disabilities within the company. Our work environment is completely adapted to different needs. We work actively with policies and guidelines regarding compensations, every year we do salary mapping, follow up and accept no differences regarding gender or other discriminating causes. As a company it is our duty to adapt and be flexible regarding parental leave and be able to work combined with being a parent, which for us means flexible work hours and environment. In 2019 there were no reported cases of discrimination.

Heléne Kry, HR and Talent Management Director

Anti-corruption and ethics

Events, gifts and activities arranged in order to strengthen and build relationships shall be made in good faith and in compliance with the Gina Tricot framework. Gina Tricot follows Swedish tax law and regulations for the value of any gifts or events. This is communicated to our employees every year as a friendly reminder. We have not had any corruption cases during 2019.

Gina Tricot strives to maintain a transparent business climate and high business ethics. We value the safety and respect of everyone affected by our business. We inform all of our employees that we have a Whistleblowing Centre which provides an opportunity to report suspicions of misconduct; anything that is not in line with our values and policies.

Our whistleblowing service is an early warning system to reduce risks. It is an important tool to foster high ethical standards and maintain customer and public confidence in us. We encourage our employees to first contact a manager in our organisation but if they feel that they cannot be open with their information, we offer the option of reporting their concern anonymously.

Health & security at Gina Tricot

All Gina Tricot stores, warehouses and the head office report workplace related accidents and incidents to HR. We continuously work on security and the work environment in our stores, warehouses and offices, this includes training, store visits, unannounced audits, and security checks with a focus on e.g. fire protection.

During 2019, we had 13 reported accidents and work-related absences, and 5,9% sick leave. Total staff turnover 2019 was 30%.

For the sake of our employees we have chosen not to present accidents and work-related absences per country. The majority, 97%, of our employees are female so that's why we have chosen not to present statistics per gender.

Long-term and permanent goals for the security department are to work for a safe and secure workplace for our employees and customers.

Corporate employees: 1,760

97% female, 3% male
 < 30 years: 68%
 30-50 years: 31%
 > 50 years: 1%

Head office: 171
 92% female, 8% male
 < 30 years: 37%
 30-50 years: 59%
 > 50 years: 4%

Stores; 1 532
 100% female, 0% male
 < 30 years: 69%
 30-50 years: 30%
 > 50 years: 1%

Ware house 47
 57% female, 43% male
 < 30 years: 68%
 30-50 years: 32%
 > 50 years: 0%

Management group: 8

63% female 37% male
 < 30 years; 0%
 30-50 years: 75%
 > 50 years: 25%

Board: 8

25% female 75% male
 < 30 years; 13%
 30-50 years: 50%
 > 50 years: 37%

Product

Offering our customers more sustainable products that respect animal rights and are safe from a customer perspective is a main focus in our daily product development.

We love more sustainable materials

"In 2019, 57% (47%) of our products were manufactured from more sustainable materials. We are glad to see that the increase follows our targets, and look forward to future challenges and reaching 100% by 2028!"

**Global Production and Sourcing Manager
Emma Garrote**

A product that we today classify as more sustainable needs to be made from a minimum of 50% more sustainable fibers. For 2028 a more sustainable product needs to be made of 100% more sustainable materials. The fibres we use and classify as more sustainable are; Better Cotton (BCI), EcoVero®, Organic Cotton, Polylana®, TENCEL®, Recycled fibers, and Regenerated fibres (viscose, lyocell, cupro) from producers with green ranking in Canopy's Hot Button report. The fibres we aim to increase the most are organic fibres, recycled fibres as well as fully-traceable fibres.

Distribution of more sustainable fibres

In our material strategy we have established clear targets for the materials used in our products, with the aim of increasing the percentage of sustainable materials that have a lower environmental impact. It motivates us to continually search for and select better materials, along with sourcing new, more environmentally-friendly materials.

Sustainable fibre targets

- 100% more sustainable products by 2028
- Steadily increase the amount of organic cotton in our sustainable cotton
- Search for new fibres to replace cotton
- Steadily increase the amount of traceable regenerated fibres
- 50% recycled polyester by 2025
- Continuously find new and innovative fibres that are more sustainable

Labelling sustainable products

During 2019 we started to implement our new sustainability communication to consumers, this will be visible on products from 2020. By communicating third-party certification logos on our products in a clearer way we believe it will be easier for our customers to make more informed choices and be able to see the differences more easily.

Cotton

Cotton is one of our most important textile fibres. At Gina Tricot, 44% of our products are made from cotton. With the environmental impact of conventional cotton in mind, our goal for 2020 is for 100% of the cotton we use to be 'more sustainable' cotton, which for us means organic cotton, recycled cotton and cotton from the Better Cotton Initiative (BCI). By the end of 2019 we reached 96% (94%).

We are now looking to the future and will raise the bar for ourselves once again. We consider BCI to be a good first step, but in coming years our goal is to shift big parts of our production from BCI to organic cotton. The knowledge that changing cotton to a wood-based fibre could reduce the water footprint by around 90% also means we're looking into ways of substituting the cotton with other, environmentally friendly fibres.

Cotton from the Better Cotton initiative 91.5% (94%)
Organic Cotton 8.5% (6%)

BCI is a training programme based on the best methods for more sustainable farming. BCI trains farmers in transitioning to and moving towards a more conservation-focused approach to water, chemicals and pesticides. This enables harvest sales to continue during the transition period, securing the schooling of the family's children.

For more information see bettercotton.org.

In total over 145,000 women were trained through BCI in health & safety, labour, gender or other social issues. In total over 88,000 women were trained in the preparation and use of pesticides (for the 2017-2018 season).

Gina Tricot sources cotton globally, with exemption of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Syria. Trading cotton with these countries has been banned by Gina Tricot for many years, due to the lack of transparency and possible presence of child labour, forced labour and under aged workers in the value chain.

In total during 2017-2018 BCI farmers in China, India, Pakistan, Tadjikistan and Turkey used less water for irrigation than comparison farmers:

China	India	Pakistan	Tajikistan	Turkey
< 18%	< 10%	< 17%	< 3%	< 4%

Viscose

Gina Tricot is committed to providing its customers with sustainable garments in fabrics that they love. Accordingly, we have set a target to buy 100% of all regenerated cellulose fibres from more sustainable sources by 2020. By this we mean recycled viscose or that the wood used to produce pulp comes from FSC certified forests, and we have minimised the use of chemicals and maximised the efficient use of water through recycling. As a member of CanopyStyles, we follow their Hot Button report which helps us to work with our viscose supply chain and take steps towards a chain that's free of viscose manufactured from wood that comes from endangered forests.

"Currently, 94% (89%) of our products are made from more sustainable regenerated cellulosic fibres. We keep pushing for improvements, and during 2019 we also started mapping the exact country of origin for all the viscose fibres used in production, and started to nominate the production units with even better environmental practice."

CSR and Quality Manager Rebecca Watkins

Polyester

One of the most important fibre challenges that Gina Tricot is currently trying to overcome is how to convert our use of normal polyester in our products to more sustainable polyester, recycled polyester. We need to take the same journey for recycled polyester as we have taken so successfully for more sustainable cotton and regenerated cellulosic fibres. We need to increase our sources of this fibre in order to break through the usage of recycled polyester in our products. We can see from the figures that we are slowly increasing the amount of recycled polyester bought, and for 2020 we hope to see an exponential growth.

Natural fibres from animals

We love animals! We therefore banned cashmere during 2019 since footage was released exposing the brutality of the shearing process. We will always distance ourselves from any activities associated with cruelty to animals! Previously banned materials are mohair, angora, fur, feathers, bone and horn. We accept leather only from a handful of nominated tanneries in China, and only as a by-product from the meat industry and from suppliers following the OIE (World Organisation for Animal Health) animal welfare standards listed below.

Gina Tricot has signed the Swedish Trade Federation's Animal Welfare Policy and we require all our partners in all parts of the supply chain to comply. We do not yet have full traceability on all our animal-based materials, but we are constantly striving to improve our sourcing methods.

Gina Tricot requires all of its partners working with animals under human control to respect the OIE (World Organisation for Animal Health) animal welfare standards, which have been formulated as Five Freedoms:

- Freedom from hunger, malnutrition and thirst;
- Freedom from fear and distress;
- Freedom from physical and thermal discomfort;
- Freedom from pain, injury and disease; and
- Freedom to express normal patterns of behaviour.

Since 2011 we are a proud member of Fur Free Retail. Gina Tricot cosmetics are not tested on animals.

For further information on the restrictions we have on animal textile fibres kindly visit our webpage www.ginatricot.com

The Nordic Swan Ecolabel

In the autumn of 2019, Gina Tricot started to work with the Nordic Swan Ecolabel. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is one of the world's top ecolabels. It is a Type 1 ecolabel, which means it's an independent organisation that works according to the life cycle perspective and with a holistic view when criteria are developed. It's also controlled by the ISO 14024 standard (learn more at: www.svanen.se).

So far Gina Tricot has had one denim order produced with this very strict ecolabel. Our vision is to have most of our basics produced under this certification including the denim and jersey collection. Right now, some of our most important key business partners in Turkey and Bangladesh are working with the entire production chain to get the certifications ready.

"We want to be a part of a better and more sustainable textile industry. To have more transparency and control of crucial parts of production such as chemicals and water usage is a good start. We know that the Nordic Swan Ecolabel certification is very tough, but it's worth all the effort in the end." Bumin Fisek, Kardem Tekstil Ltd

Safe, high quality styles

"Ensuring high product quality is one of our most important components in our overall sustainability efforts."

Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager

We are constantly evaluating each product and quality is an important parameter that is considered throughout the development process. All products fall under our quality, chemical and safety requirements. Together with our purchase and design teams we continuously perform a product risk assessment with the precautionary principle in mind and evaluate which products we need to put extra effort into. For example, together we decide which products to test at a third-party laboratory for quality, which ones to perform quality controls in production on and which products require extra care information to be provided to customers. All Gina Tricot suppliers must sign a written agreement that they comply with our quality requirements prior to any production. We perform third-party tests at selected laboratories, conduct tests at our own facilities and perform testing on site at our suppliers.

Sustainable product targets

- All products shall have a long life length and fit in a circular system
- Continuously offer new challenging ways for customers to consume more sustainable fashion
- Increase the collection of garments from customers, our goal is to collect 25% by 2028
- Implement a way of working that prolongs the life of garments after customer use

All Gina Tricot production in Bangladesh is 100% quality controlled by our own local staff, in other production countries we perform random quality controls based on our product risk assessment. All of these efforts aim to achieve the highest possible level of quality.

In 2019, we performed over 1,000 quality controls of our products in production.

We also nominate specific quality assessed trim and thread suppliers, tanneries for leather production and fabric suppliers to ensure the quality level and the chemical content used in production. We constantly monitor customer claims, and for 2019 0.48% (0.28%) of all sold products were returned with complaints regarding quality. During 2019, we withdrew four products from stores due to quality issues, one due to chemical issues and two due to safety issues.

We have identified customer behaviour as having a big part in our product's lives. As a part of our effort to increase customer knowledge on textile qualities and doing laundry the right way to prolong the life of our products, we worked on our new sustainability webpage, which will be launched in 2020. A part of this webpage is dedicated to product care, with tips on how to treat your garments as well as products that will simplify this. During 2020, we will increase communication to customers regarding their part in our sustainability journey and ways to minimise their environmental impact.

Product safety

In 2019, we proudly launched our first collection of children's wear.

"Selling products to children means we have an even bigger responsibility to only release products on the market that are safe. By this, we mean general product safety, along with safe chemical content. Children should be able to play and climb freely, without any risks being posed from the clothes we sell."
CSR and Quality Manager Rebecca Watkins

Every one of our children's wear products are assessed according to safety aspects. At Gina Tricot, this is of highest impor-

tance and we are constantly striving to improve these parameters. Throughout the production process, we have set internal routines and supplier guidelines in order to ensure safe production and products. We have also held internal children safety training courses for our colleagues developing the products.

All products comply with the requirements of the European standards regarding children's safety, EN 14682 and TR 16792. We do not allow any hand-sewn or glued on details, and all buttons and details are third-party tested so that they are securely attached. Hoods must be detachable on all outerwear, except for baby sizes, and cord and drawstring lengths are monitored and follow the recommended lengths. Moreover, all our children's wear products must follow our unisex policy, and be so comfortable that your kid doesn't want to take their favourite off when going to bed.

For every Gina Tricot product, we carefully select materials and ensure that no legally restricted hazardous chemical substances are used in production. We do this through several types of testing prior to production; through our production offices, on site at our suppliers and at third-party laboratories. We conduct these tests to ensure that our chemical requirements have been met and to ban any non-conforming product prior to the production stage. During our site visits we also control the chemical inventory.

To supplement these efforts, we continuously perform chemical spot tests from Sweden. If we were to find any prohibited chemical substances above the legal limits, the products would be recalled from stores, and destroyed. This is the only instance where Gina Tricot would destroy a product, rather than try to reuse or recycle it. Thankfully, this rarely occurs, and in 2019 one discovery was made resulting in product destruction.

All Gina Tricot suppliers must sign a written agreement that they comply with our chemical restriction list, and requirements based on REACH regulation EC No 1907/2006. We always apply the restrictions from the strictest sales country throughout the supply chain. We strive to remain up-to-date on the latest developments through collaboration with, for example, RISE Chemicals Group and the Swedish Chemicals Agency.

Denim

Denim is one of the most important product groups for Gina Tricot, and one of the most loved by our customers. We also know that denim production relies heavily on wet processing and therefore has a high climate impact. During 2019, 100% of our denim products were produced using more sustainable materials.

Our strategy for denim includes continuously using more sustainable materials and using the best available technologies for wet processing.

Sustainable denim targets

- 100% more sustainable wet processing methods by 2021
- Increase the amount of Nordic Swan Ecolabel certified styles
- Increase the amount of recycled materials
- Challenge regular denim production with alternative materials to cotton
- Facilitate circularity

One of our biggest denim suppliers, Maydenim, has invested in the latest technology for the best available and more environmentally-friendly production methods. This huge investment leads to an environmental win of energy savings, chemicals savings, and least 25-35% water savings.

Planet

We know that fashion has a big impact on the climate. As a player on the global fashion scene, we are constantly looking for new ways to make the best use of resources and minimise our climate impact.

Circular fashion

The fashion industry has had a rude awakening in recent years when it comes to the big climate impact that we are all part of. At Gina Tricot, we are very humble and know that we are a part of the problem, but we also know that we can be a part of the solution. To be able to sell truly sustainable products to our customers, we must close the loop. We need to design for the circular economy, where materials are designed with end-of-life recovery in mind from the outset. This is one of the biggest challenges and opportunities facing the fashion industry. We need to embrace a more circular fashion industry and see this as a potential new business model.

Use what we have

Many of our suppliers around the world have stockrooms filled with leftover fabrics from old collections. To see this as the treasure it really is everyone has to get involved.

In autumn 2019, we launched a collaboration with Siri Wikman's brand Aéryne, entirely made from leftover fabrics. Aéryne is a Swedish fashion brand based in Sweden with a design studio in Paris. The collections are made by women for women, and have a very strong feminine touch.

10% of the sales price for each piece in the collection was donated to UN Women, Sweden.

Design with the end in mind

The first step is to look at how we design our products. This means designing with sustainability and circularity in mind, using less fibre blends in products as well as designing for easy assembly of trimmings. Sustainability therefore needs to be implemented through design from the very beginning.

The goal is to design products that the users can wear and love for a long time, made from materials that are from better sources and produced sustainably, and that have material sustainability.

"Consider that the decisions made at the drawing board will affect the entire lifecycle of the garment. Always design for intended use and beyond."

Mistra Future Fashion, The outlook report 2011-2019

But what happens when the products reach end-of-life? Choosing materials that can be recycled is important. These materials need to be promoted in the design phase. We know that the purer the composition of the product, the easier it is to recycle. In 2019, Gina Tricot has 77% products with purer compositions (less than 10% blend).

"The collection was a challenge for us in many ways, and we had to re-think our design process. Instead of sending our requests to our suppliers, we started working by asking our suppliers what they had left."

Monika Mellin, Design Manager

Second Love

The more we use our garments, the less we need to consume and buy new clothes, and this automatically leads to less climate impact. We need to make sure our garments are worn and loved as many times as possible. We are firm believers that our garments have a long life ahead of them, preferably by multiple users. The more the merrier.

One important step involves collecting garments in Gina Tricot shops once they are worn out or are no longer wanted. The clothes need to be reused by others or recycled and sent back into the production loop as new raw materials. In line with our circular fashion commitment, we are striving to increase our collection of garments from customers by 50% by the year 2020 through different activities in store. In 2019 we collected 50 tons, which is same amount as collected 2018. Collecting garments for reusing or recycling is a crucial first step in prolonging the product's useful life or turning them into new raw materials in a never-ending loop.

Since 2012, Gina Tricot has given customers the opportunity to hand in their old and used clothes in all of its stores to ensure a second life. All clothes, including customer claims, are either donated to Human Bridge (www.humanbridge.se) or Fretex (www.fretex.no). Human Bridge is a professional organisation

involved in material aid projects. The organisation supports humanitarian crises and development assistance projects by providing money, clothing and other important materials. Our returned garments are either sent to people in need, or they are sold and the proceeds are used to fund Human Bridge's projects.

Fretex is a similar organisation in Norway, driven by the salvation army, where the collected garments from Gina Tricot's Norwegian stores end up. Out of the garments collected by Fretex, 78% is re-sold in their own stores, 20% is used for material recycling and 2% cannot be recycled or re-sold. We also sell some clothes to Shoes and Clothes. They purchase our unsold stock or returned items in order to resell the garments second-hand. Gina Tricot then donates 100% of the revenue from such sales to charitable organisations working with various aspects of sustainability.

Our aim is to minimise the number of our products that end up here, through unsold garments, customer claims or purchasing errors, however the goal is to increase the collected garments from customers.

Customised and repaired denim with Repamera

Henning Gillberg, VD Repamera

With denim being one of our customers' most loved product categories, we tried to give them something extra during 2019.

We teamed up with Repamera, and together we offered customised denim pieces in one of our stores in Malmö, Sweden. We believe that when fitting has been optimised to perfection you will use the denim much longer and treat it with care.

We also sent all denim customer claims to Repamera for repair, instead of giving customers new denim pieces. This represents a great environmental gain, and also sends an important message to customers that the denim still has a value and can be repaired rather than discarded.

Repamera is an e-commerce tailor service that is based in Malmö, Sweden. Their professional and experienced tailors are all immigrants from countries in conflict who have found their first full-time employment at Repamera. Collaborations like this repair not only jeans, but also people.

"Through good collaborations we can make the fashion industry more circular, which is good for both clothing companies and mother earth."

Henning Gillberg, VD Repamera

Upcycle by Gina Tricot

Together with the research project Re:Textile, XV Production and Färgeriet EK, former Korallen, Gina Tricot launched an upcycled collection made from customer claims and garments with defects. These products and materials would normally have been donated to our partners working with garment reuse, but this time they were given a chance to have a second life. Re:Textile and XV Production set up a micro factory at the Swedish School of Textiles where the old garments were remade. This collection was sewn and launched online within three weeks. The collection was small in terms of the number of pieces, but an important test to give us the confidence to look for a scale-up possibility in the near future. For Gina Tricot, this was also a way to try new and more sustainable business models, and to highlight the importance of circular design internally.

Re:newcell

Some major breakthroughs in science have been made in textile recycling and Gina Tricot is following these developments closely, through participation in industry initiatives and research projects.

The technology for sorting different types of fibres and reusing them needs to occur in full scale production units. All fibres and garments have value in a closed loop system and Gina Tricot wants to ensure that none of our products end up in landfills or are burnt. Our goal is to offer sustainable, quality-assured products that appeal to our customers. We want fashion to be produced and consumed in a never-ending loop, and Re:newcell is one company that works using circular processes.

In 2018, Gina Tricot started to cooperate and support Re:newcell, pioneers in the recycling industry. Re:newcell uses cotton waste to produce a pure, natural and biodegradable raw material that can then be turned into new clothes of the highest quality – and recycled again and again. Re:newcell opened their first recycling plant in 2017 in Kristinehamn, Sweden. At the plant, they can recycle 7,000 tones of textile waste each year. That's enough to make 30 million brand new t-shirts!

In 2019, Gina Tricot donated 36 066,5 kg (6849 kg) of to Re:newcell's factory with the help of three different suppliers in the world, Maydenim Tekstil San Ve Dis Ticaret Ltd Sti, Baykanlar Tekstil Sanayi Ve Ticaret Anonim Sirketi, Shasha Garments Ltd, ready to be turned into new textile fibres to be used over and over again. Making clothes from wastage is a dream that will soon become reality! The aim is to make clothes from wastage that will already be in stores in 2020, and then gradually increase the amount.

RENT your party outfit

We all need to consume less and explore other more sustainable ways, not in the future but now. We know for a fact that we need to use our clothes more, and one way to consume more sustainably is to rent your garments instead of buying them. Twice as many uses per garment lifecycle eliminated almost 50% of impact.

In spring 2019 Gina Tricot launched a new business model called RENT. The business concept was first tested in one store at the Femman shopping centre in Gothenburg, Sweden. And in December, 2019 the business model was expanded to two more stores, Linköping and Stockholm.

We started the concept with party clothes since party clothes are also occasion wear and normally a bit more expensive than everyday clothes, and might therefore be of more interest to rent for our customers. It's a good way for us to test the market and see if there is a new business opportunity. So far, it's an ongoing business case study, but we already have ideas for how we can develop the offer to our customers during the coming year.

"It's also a great way to test and actually wear the clothes before you as a customer make up your mind whether you want to keep the garment or not. This will eliminate the number of wrong buys and clothes that are not used."

Emma Garrote, Global Production and Sustainability Manager

Agnes Steingruber, Buying Assistant Gina Tricot

Care for the planet

Climate change is the biggest challenge we face. All our production, transport, travel and facilities involve emissions and impact the size of our carbon footprint.

80% of the environmental impact from textiles comes from the production phase according to Mistra Future Fashion. This means that we, as a brand, have a huge responsibility in decreasing this and implementing the best available, more environmentally friendly techniques in production. If we look closer at production, wet processes are the part of production with the highest climate impact. This part of production affects not only climate through its GHG (Green House Gas) emissions, but also uses a large amount of water and chemicals.

"We have updated our sustainability commitments, and as one part of our climate strategy we will look deeper into our suppliers' wet processes. We will start by measuring the climate impact, and continue by taking actions to minimise it."
Global Production and Sustainability Manager Emma Garrote.

As part of our overall climate efforts, Gina Tricot is a founding member of the Swedish Textile Initiative for Climate Action, STICA. This is a platform for Swedish textile companies and organisations to understand our climate impact and learn best practices on how to tackle it. We must examine our impact throughout the entire value chain and work hard to minimise the climate impact of our entire business.

Gina Tricot commits to, at minimum, reduce our greenhouse gases in line with 1.5 C warming pathway.

The network's efforts are aligned with the UN Framework on Climate Change's Paris Agreement, and the goals within STICA are to:

- Understand all aspects of our climate impact
- Measure our greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions

- Develop science-based targets and plans for reducing our GHG emissions in line with 1.5°C warming pathway.
- Develop a process and structure for reporting and communicating our organisation's progress
- Identify actions that generate business benefits and organise collaborative projects aimed at reducing emissions in parts of the value chain that are beyond our direct control

"During 2020, we will look deeper into our supply chain and the climate impact it has. We will start by measuring the impact we have today and primarily do all we can to minimise the use of resources. We will also set strategies and goals for how to reduce our impact."

Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager

We shall always look for better production technologies, better energy sources, better chemicals, better materials and better ways to transport our products from production and also home to our customers.

Measuring our climate impact

Our carbon footprint calculations follows the Greenhouse Gas Protocol. In 2019 we put extra efforts into measuring our scope 1 and 2 emissions as well as parts of scope 3. We will broaden the measurement of scope 3 in 2020, with focus on the emissions linked to production.

- Scope 1 emissions are direct emissions that come from sources owned or controlled by Gina Tricot, like our company vehicles.
- Scope 2 emissions are indirect emissions that come from purchased energy, like the energy used for our offices and stores.
- Scope 3 emissions are all indirect emissions, excluding scope 2, from the value chain such as product transport, business travel and emissions from producing products. For 2019, we only measured business travel and transportation of goods in Scope 3.

Energy consumption by country (mWh) Scope 1 and 2

	2019
Bangladesh	21
China	11
Denmark	962
Finland	1,950
Germany	1,142
Norway	2,109
Sweden*	7,233
TOTAL	13,428
	2018
China	N/A
Bangladesh	N/A
Denmark	1,119
Finland	1,571
Germany	1,286
Norway	2,694
Sweden*	6,385
TOTAL	13,055
	2017
Bangladesh	N/A
China	N/A
Denmark	260
Finland	1,200
Germany	3,534
Norway	2,383
Sweden*	7,938
TOTAL	15,315

*The figures cover all stores in all five countries. In Sweden, we also include the warehouse, head office and PR office. In Bangladesh and China the figures represent our production offices. Electricity consumption is reported including heating for all countries (information from landlords), reporting also includes estimated figures from stores where we do not own the energy contract. In total we increased our energy use by 2,9% compared with 2018, the main reason is this years inclusion of district cooling as well as production offices in Bangladesh and China as well as PR office in Stockholm.

Distribution of total carbon emissions (tons CO₂e)

	2019
Company operated vehicles, scope 1	33
Electricity for heating, district heating and district cooling, scope 2	16
Business trips, scope 3	248
Freight Shipments, scope 3	2,719
TOTAL	3,016
	2018
Company operated vehicles, scope 1	42
Electricity for heating, District heating, scope 2	19
Business trips, scope 3	255
Freight Shipments, scope 3	1,689
TOTAL	2,005
	2017
Company operated vehicles, scope 1	39
Electricity for heating and District heating, scope 2	21
Business trips, scope 3	233
Freight Shipments, scope 3	1,526
TOTAL	1,819

During 2019, we managed to minimize the carbon emissions for our business trips, Electricity use as well as company operated vehicles. Unfortunately we had challenges with intermodal transport, leading to increased transport by land. We also suffered from lack of in-time deliveries and capacity problems for train transports from China. Unfortunately this lead to an increase use of air as transportation method. Both these parameters lead to increased carbon emissions over all during 2019.

Water

Water is a fundamental component of textile manufacturing. To be able to produce fibres and fabrics, and wash and dye garments we rely heavily on water. But clean water is scarce in many places around the world, and water is also essential for all living life on earth. We must manage our precious resources carefully and responsibly, ensure availability and clean water and sanitation for all. Today, billions of people are still lacking clean water as well as sanitation services.

"Gina Tricot wants to be a positive power in terms of water management. We want our suppliers to use water more efficiently, recycle and reuse as much wastewater as possible and make sure all wastewater is free from any unwanted chemicals."

Global Production and Sustainability Manager Emma Garrote

Our choice of fibres also affects water usage dramatically. The fibre with the highest impact on water scarcity is without a doubt cotton. This is yet another reason to look towards replacing this fibre with more water friendly fibres.

Customers can also contribute by using water more carefully during washing, primarily by washing garments less frequently and instead focusing on stain removal and airing garments. During 2019, we teamed up with the World Wildlife Foundation, WWF, in their WWF Fashion Water Stewardship Pledge.

Sustainable climate and water targets

- Conclude external environmental audits at 100% of the suppliers with wet processing units
- Implement Manufacturing Restricted Substance List, MRSL, on 100% of all wet processing units
- 100% of all wet processing units in our supply chain shall be more resource effective and reuse and recycle water

During 2019, we signed up to the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) Fashion Water Stewardship Pledge.

Under the pledge we will:

- Assess water risks in our supply chain. Understand challenges and communicate these risks.
- Implement industry best practices with all our wet processing units in our supply chain.
- Join water stewardship collective action programme, working beyond factories and addressing root causes of challenges in areas of production.

We have started to use WWF's online tool the Water Risk Filter (WRF), which empowers us as a brand to explore, assess and respond to water risks in our supply chain. This is the first step towards setting a strategy, a more sustainable and responsible use of water in our supply chain. We have started to analyze one of our biggest denim producers in Turkey and its water intense facilities.

We have collected data including the amount of used, which type of water, how much was discharged and where the water was discharged. By using the WRF, we can see both the operational and basin water risks related to the facility that was analyzed. For 2020 we will take actions to address these risks as well as to expand the number of units to be assessed using the tool.

Through partnerships, Gina Tricot shall increase access to clean water. Through our unique collaboration with UNICEF we are providing 20,000 children and parents or caregivers with hygiene promotion messages and access to safely managed sanitation facilities. An extra 300 children and parents or caregivers were also covered by access to safe water and sanitation through built WASH blocks.

Inspiring customers to become more sustainable

Swedish consumption of textiles is increasing, and unfortunately the garments are not handled with the care they deserve, but used with a throwaway mentality. During the last 17 years the consumption of textiles in Sweden has increased by 30% per capita, and we can see that fully functional clothes are being thrown away.

"Gina Tricot is responsible for how our products are made, and we have the responsibility of setting demands and pushing our suppliers towards more sustainable production methods. We are aware of this responsibility and the challenges that come along with it. We are determined to minimise the negative climate impact that our production has. But, we must not forget that customers share our responsibility and must be part of the solution."

CSR and Quality Manager Rebecca Watkins.

During 2019, the Mistra Future Fashion (MFF) report "Environmental assessment of Swedish clothing consumption - six garments, sustainable futures" was released showing very clear data of Swedish textile consumption and the environmental impact it has. These are new figures to us which show the transformation that needs to take place. We as a brand, as well as our customers, need to re-think how we use fashion.

Our care labels have for many years recommended less-frequent washing and washing at cooler temperatures. In the new MFF report however, we can see that the environmental impact from washing clothes at home in Sweden is low, at only 3%. This is due to the generally good energy sources we have in the country. The best thing we can do is to wash garments less frequently, and instead focus on local stain removal and airing garments. In autumn 2019, we launched our product line Care For. These products from the Laundry Society aim to increase the awareness of customer responsibility linked to garment care. The range includes fresheners and stain removers. We also started selling Guppyfriend, allowing customers to minimise their microfibre pollution after washing. To see the products, go to www.ginatricot.com

From a customer perspective we need to be more sure of the garments we consume, use them more and treat them better. The goal must be to prolong the garment's life. If you need a garment for a one-off event – rent it.

When you want to move on from your garment, it is important to pass it on so it can enjoy a second life. After a while we will need to repair the product, and maybe also upcycle it. If products are treated with the love and care they deserve, they will last longer. First when the garment is truly worn out should we pass it on for recycling of the fibres. This new way of thinking opens up many more opportunities for you to love your products, but in different forms.

"We have seen and truly understood the need for improved communication with customers regarding their part, in order to minimise each product's sustainability impact. The more we can help customers prolong their product's lives, the better. Our collaboration with the Laundry Society is an example of how we try to inform customers to give a little extra love to their garments" Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager.

During 2019, we launched several different projects to challenge the customers way of consuming. We will continue our efforts in 2020 by adding activities that will activate our customers' wardrobes and make sure that their old Gina Tricot garments will have less wardrobe time and more wear time.

Addressing the problem of overproduction

Since 2017, we worked progressively on reducing over production and the number of pieces produced. From an financial point of view, this is to reduce the number of garments sold to a reduced price. From a sustainability point of view, it's mainly to minimise overproduction. We think this is a very good example of how financial and environmental sustainability go hand in hand and how they're a win-win for everyone. Our price level has increased, but we have filled our products with more sustainable materials and processes, and they are of higher quality. At the same time our turnover has increased.

	Volume	Average garment price	Sustainable materials
2019	-17%	+8%	57%
2018	-14 %	+2%	47%
2017	100%	100%	45%

If we use our garments, in their original form, twice as much as on average – the environmental impact on a national level will decrease by 49%.

If a customer walks or rides their bicycle to go and buy a product instead of driving a car – this means a minimum environmental impact reduction of 12% for the average distance.

Plastic and packaging

We will always need some type of packaging materials in order to receive our goods in good condition from suppliers, however we need to look over all the ways of packaging and use the materials more efficiently and see where we can minimise their use. With that in mind Gina Tricot signed Canopy's Pack4Good Statement. As part of the Pack4Good initiative, we have set ambitious goals to help address the world's climate crisis and wave of species extinctions.

We are committed to ensuring that by the end of 2022 all of our packaging is:

- Designed to reduce material use
- Free of materials from ancient and endangered forests.
- Uses a maximum of recycled or Next Generation Solution sourced fibres, (this includes fibre from agricultural residues or microbial cellulose).

We are still part of One Bag Habit where our main goals are to:

- Provide customers with more sustainable shopping bags
- Minimise the use of shopping bags
- Donate the surplus from sales

During 2019, we donated over 2.4 SEK M from the One Bag Habit initiative. We donated 100% of the surplus to UNICEF. We also minimised the sales of total shopping bags by 10% during 2019, with a total saving of about 40 tons of plastic.

During 2019, Gina Tricot focused on investigating our plastic use. We have started to identify our biggest opportunities for avoiding plastics in our value chain chain that would make the most impact. We strive to work on removing as many unnecessary packaging materials as possible. In order to achieve a more sustainable plastic use we need to use materials smarter and more sparingly.

In January 2019, Gina Tricot stopped producing our traditional plastic shopping bag. Instead we developed and produced a shopping bag made from recycled FSC branded paper. All of the plastic bags already produced will be used before the change to paper bags. The decision was made based on the fact that paper is 100% biodegradable, and we want to minimise plastic littering which causes serious problems for animals and the environment. This decision saves us about 65 tons of plastic every year.

Packaging

During 2019, we met several suppliers of packaging material to learn more about the future packaging materials with less environmental impact. Our current online shipping bags are made from 80% recycled plastics. Our goal for 2020 is to start using online shipping bags made of recycled FSC certified paper.

In order to reduce plastics today we have started to buy some product categories without polybags. We know that plastic free logistics offers the fashion industry a great potential to save plastic from being used and produced. In 2019 we started to test sending our garment orders with less plastic packaging from their production country to Sweden. Our goal is to only use plastic packaging when it's absolutely necessary in order for our garment quality to be maintained. After minimising the use of polybags, we will look into the possibility of changing the necessary polybags to more environmentally friendly options.

Addressing microplastics

In 2019, Gina Tricot also started to sell Guppyfriend, a washing bag that is the first solution to preventing microfibres from entering into rivers and oceans. It protects and thus extends the lifetime of textiles. Fewer fibres break and the bag itself doesn't lose any fibres. The fibres that do break during washing are captured inside the bag and can easily be removed with the aim of minimising microplastics from commercial laundering. As part of the three-year MinShed research project led by RISE, we are also trying to play a part in finding solutions to minimise the release of microplastics from textiles. The goal of the project is to create knowledge and guidelines to help the textile industry to design and create clothes made of synthetic materials which do not emit microplastics. The project will also investigate how washing machines are designed and whether or not they can be equipped with a filter to reduce the emissions of microplastics.

Constructing a more sustainable store experience

Our stores are the primary contact where our customer meets Gina Tricot. This contact shall mediate our values within sustainability and send a positive and empowering feeling to our customers. Today we have 170 stores in 99 cities and five countries. During 2019, we opened one new flagship store in Copenhagen. We implemented FSC certified wooden hangers in 4 stores during 2019 and will implement it in all new stores receiving our new store concept. For the rest of our stores we have recycled and recyclable hangers that are part of a closed loop. All our products in more sustainable materials are clearly marked with hangtags to inform customers about fibre content and also to simplify the decision-making, so it's easier to make a better choice. We are constantly updating store lights to LEDs. For 2020, the objective when it comes to lighting is to change to LED in at least 10 units, which will include new shops, relocations, and/or refurbishments (touch-ups).

"The effects of LED is positive from several aspects, including the reduction of energy and hence cooling but also the conceptual angle with a better light spread. For 2019, the result is that 30% of our shops converted to LED or had LED installed."
Jessica Syrén, Head of Expansion.

Since 2016, we have a handbook for all our suppliers of non-commercial goods and services covering social, ethical and environmental requirements from Gina Tricot including a supplier self-assessment on environmental and social issues. In 57 % of our stores we oversee the electricity contract. In all of those stores we have green electricity from renewable sources like water and wind.

Sustainable expansion and construction targets

- To have the most efficient and energy-saving lighting equipment in all stores.
- To use 50% recycled materials for furnishings and fittings.

Towards more sustainable logistic

Our production is global. Different production markets have special skills and all of them are needed to produce the variety of products we offer our customers. We also have stores in five countries, and a European webpage. All of this leads to a lot of logistics that we need to manage in an environmentally smart way, which most of the time also leads to financial savings as well.

When we transport the products from our production countries, we have a clear policy to use the most environmentally friendly options, with sea transport always being the best option. Today all cartons are full, and the percentage of air is minimum. During 2019 we suffered from lack of in-time deliveries and capacity problems for train transports from China. Unfortunately this led to an increased use of air as transportation method. Forward we have taken drastic methods to minimize air as transportation method. Both from a financial and environmental point of view, air transports are both expensive and has high emissions.

More and more customers choose to pick up their online order in one of our stores. To save the environment and number of shipments we pack all customer orders to one shop in the same carton. We have also decreased the number of pick-ups of store orders from five days to three times a week. This means 40% less shipments.

If an online customer wants to return something, they can do so directly in the store instead of sending it back to our distribution centre in Borås. All the returns that are not handled in a store are sent back to our distribution centre in Borås. We handle all returns in-house to avoid any additional transport from external partners.

Today we distribute garments to our stores five days a week, but we will evaluate if that's necessary in the future. The aim is to reduce the number of distribution days to three or four to reduce the environmental impact.

Greenhouse gas emissions by mode of transport, tons CO₂e.

	2019
Air*	1,717 ton*
Sea	266 ton
Land**	705 ton**
Rail	3 ton
Intermodal***	28 ton
	2018
Air*	592 ton*
Sea	314 ton
Land**	662 ton
Rail	8 ton
Intermodal***	113 ton
	2017
Air*	280 ton*
Sea	446 ton
Land**	745 ton
Rail	0 ton
Intermodal***	55 ton

*includes sea/air

**WTW, Well-to-Wheel, total impact of fuel production (well-to-tank, WTT) as well as the impact of the vehicle use (tank-to-wheel TTW).

***Multiple modes of transportation combined; in our case land, rail and sea. Calculations according to EN 16258. Calculations are a combination of PostNord business data, Ekol business data, GEODIS business data, aggregated modelled values from EcoTransIT and carrier specific values from Clean Cargo.

During 2019, we still had challenges with intermodal transport, leading to increased transport by land. We also had challenges with rail, leading to increased air transport.

We also suffered from lack of in-time deliveries and capacity problems for train transports from China. Unfortunately this led to an increase use of air as transportation method.

Distribution of greenhouse gas emissions by mode of transport

	2019
Air*	63,1 %
Sea	9,8 %
Land	25,9 %
Rail	0,1 %
Intermodal	1,1 %
	2018
Air*	35 %
Sea	18,5 %
Land	39 %
Rail	0,5 %
Intermodal	7 %
	2017
Air*	18 %
Sea	29 %
Land	49 %
Rail	0 %
Intermodal	4 %

*includes sea/air

Distribution of shipments based on number of purchased goods, by mode of transport

	2019
Air*	6.6 %
Sea	50.2 %
Land	34.5 %
Rail	0.2 %
Intermodal	8.5 %
	2018
Air*	3 %
Sea	55 %
Land	24 %
Rail	1 %
Intermodal	17 %
	2017
Air*	2 %
Sea	50 %
Land	21 %
Rail	0 %
Intermodal	27 %

*includes sea/air

Tables and indexes

Addressing sustainability risks

The scope of the textile industry is worldwide and it affects many people throughout the process from raw material to finished product. Besides the vast opportunities, there are also significant risks and responsibilities. Many sustainability issues pose great risks to Gina Tricot and our business as we rely on outsourcing production in risk countries as well as use vast amount of resources that are either endless or sensitive to climate change. These risks also impose great risks to people involved in Gina Tricot's supply chain as well as our customers.

All our production countries are unique. This means that there are risks specific to each country, in addition to problems that are prevalent worldwide. For 2019, we have also added two new production countries, but in general the risks are the same in these countries as in our current production countries. Below is a list of some of our most significant risks and page references where to find information on how we manage these risks.

Illegal and unhealthy overtime

Excessive overtime is the most common problem we see in our supply chain and it exists in all our production countries. We manage this through third-party audits, as well as our own internal audits. You can read more about this on pages 16-17 and 48.

Illegal and precarious working conditions

Workers are sometimes exposed to unsafe working conditions during production, meaning that their health and safety can be endangered. This could for example be insufficient ventilation or lack of personal protective equipment. Read more on how we manage this risk on pages 16, 18, 20 and 48.

Illegal and precarious employments

Another risk in many production countries is the prevalence of temporary employments. During peak season or holiday season, some suppliers tend to rely on seasonal workers. This is a problem, because typically, these types of employment situations lack stability and security. The country at the most significant risk for this is Turkey, due to the vast amount of refugees fleeing to the country from Syria. Read more on how we manage this risk on pages 16, 18 and 48.

Child labour

Some of our production countries are developing countries with widespread poverty. In these countries it is not uncommon to be forced to put your children to work, to earn extra income. The country at the most significant risk for this is Bangladesh, where family situations are often very tough, and every income a family can have is important for survival. Read more on pages 23-25 and 48 on how Gina Tricot manages this risk in production.

Illegal and unethical wages

This is the second-most common risk we see in our supply chain, and again, it applies to all our production countries. Read more about how we address this on pages 16-18, 20

and 48.

Corruption

Producing in developing countries with widespread poverty and unstable political situations also leads to increased risks of corruption. This could be for example different forms of bribery throughout the supply chain. Read more about how we address this on page 27 and 47.

Environmental pollution

Processing of textile products has a significant environmental impact. Consumption of water, chemicals and energy is high throughout the entire process. Without correct preventative work severe environmental pollution could occur. Read more on how Gina Tricot manages this on pages 29-33, 40 and 47-48.

Water overuse

Textile production is water intense. In many of our production countries water access is scarce and many of the workers lack access to clean water in their daily life. How we work with water is further described on page 40 and 48.

Climate change

Increased temperatures, flooding and droughts are some serious examples of climate change that affect humanity and the world we live in. Read more about how we address this on pages 29-30, 33, 35-39, 42-43 and 47-48.

Deforestation

Deforestation and the protection of flora and fauna in endan-

gered forests linked to wood pulp production is another risk. Read more on how we work on this on pages 30, 42 and 48.

Unsafe products

Customers need to be able to rely on product safety during use. Risks related to this could be chemical content in product or for example other safety aspects of a product. Read more on how we work with this on page 32 and 48.

Insufficient quality

Product quality is an important aspect of customer satisfaction but also of sustainability. Parameters could be a product's appearance after wash and colour fastness. Read more about how we address this on page 32 and 48.

Gina Tricot offers a wide range of products produced in several different production markets. Accordingly, it is difficult to provide a comprehensive list of all the risks. We focus our efforts on identifying the most significant risks and the best ways of managing them. Some risks are more challenging and complicated, since they might be cultural or require fundamental changes throughout the industry in a particular country.

Gina Tricot has a Code of Conduct that covers all of the topics described above. We use the code, third-party audits, our own internal audits and frequent site visits in an attempt to achieve daily improvements in production environments. Collaboration is the key to it all, for example through long-term partnerships with suppliers and by joining forces with other brands.

Collaborations and partner suppliers

From politics to production. From nationwide industrial networks to global collaboration projects and production. There are many ways of working together to make a difference. For an overview of the organisations we work together with, to drive change for sustainability please see our website

<https://www.ginatricot.com/se/hallbarhet/vara-samarbeten>

For an overview of all our partner suppliers that we work with to produce wonderful products in a more sustainable manner, please see our website

https://www.ginatricot.com/cms/work/sustainability/leverantorer-2019_update.pdf

Sustainability management table

GLOBAL GOALS	TOPICS	MANAGEMENT/POLICIES	AIM	2019 ACTIVITIES	FOLLOW-UP AND CONSEQUENCES	RESPONSIBILITY
	Animal welfare issues	We have implemented the Swedish Trade Confederation Animal Welfare Policy. The policy is a part of our general agreement with all our suppliers.	Its purpose is to ensure a long-term approach to animal materials in our products and minimise the risk of our products being linkable to unethical mistreatment or handling of animals. Implementation of the Swedish Trade Confederation Animal Welfare Policy demonstrates our stance and desire to lead industry practices.	Participation in the Swedish Trade Confederation network on animal materials. Ban on cashmere in production.	Our own supplier visits. Follow-ups of new material choices with purchasing team. Products that do not meet the requirements of our Animal Welfare Policy will be stopped in the planning stage. The consequence of failure to meet the requirements of the Animal Welfare Policy is that we will be required to remove our association with the Swedish Trade Confederation Animal Welfare Policy.	CSR and Quality Manager
	Anti-corruption	We have an internal anti-corruption policy and guidelines. Our efforts to prevent corruption and promote healthy competition are based on Swedish legislation and the Swedish anti-corruption Institute Business Code.	All the relationships our company is engaged in will be characterised by good business ethics. Putting the company's best interests ahead of lining one's own pockets makes us a better company in the long term.	General anti-corruption information communicated to employees.	Whistleblowing portal for all stores and the head office where irregularities can be reported anonymously. The portal is available to all employees in Sweden. Incident reporting via the intranet.	CFO
	Environmental impact of suppliers	amfori Code of Conduct Environmental policy Climate and water strategy	The aim is to ensure an environmentally efficient production process in which our environmental requirements are met and/or exceeded. Both short-term and long-term environmental gains are rewarded.	amfori audits, our own supplier visits and WWF WRF mapping. Participation in Better Cotton and Cotton Connect.	Part of supplier evaluation and production planning where we strive to give preference to suppliers with good environmental initiatives. If we discover that our environmental requirements are systematically not met, all production with the supplier in question will be suspended.	Production and Sustainability Manager CSR and Quality Manager
	Economic performance	Internal financial goals.	The aim is to ensure a financially sustainable business over time. Ensuring that the business delivers according to its goals and the expectations of its owners, board and management.	Quarterly forecasts.	Audits and monthly checks with the board and owners. The consequence of failure to meet financial goals will be corrective action plans to ensure goal attainment.	CEO
	Energy and air emissions	Sustainability strategy Transport policy Travel policy Green electricity contract at head office and stores with their own green contracts.	The purpose of our efforts is to ensure that we reduce the environmental impact of our business. Our product transport activities from the production country to sales markets have a significant negative impact on our climate. We also have some impact in relation to our own energy use.	Corrective actions in accordance with energy mapping. Efforts to reduce the amount of air shipments. Increase the share of company cars that are clean vehicles.	Map environmental impact and set clear goals through STICA. Climate compensation for part of our known GHG emission impact during 2019. Monthly follow-up of modes of transport and follow-up of travel. Annual review of energy consumption. The reasons for any increases in air shipments must be explained. Air transport must not be used systematically. Increases in energy use must be explained and corrective action must be taken as soon as possible.	Logistics Manager HR Manager Head of Expansion Purchasing Manager

GLOBAL GOALS	TOPICS	MANAGEMENT/POLICIES	AIM	2019 ACTIVITIES	FOLLOW-UP AND CONSEQUENCES	RESPONSIBILITY
	Materials	Sustainability strategy 2028 material goals Purchasing strategy Animal Welfare Policy Material strategy, Product strategy, Packaging material strategy, Climate and water strategy	The aim is to ensure that the materials chosen for our products meet our quality requirements and contribute to our goal of only using environmentally sustainable products by 2028.	Quality goal (<1% returns) Training and follow-up meetings with purchasers. Maintaining a materials library of base qualities. Finding new more sustainable materials, increase amount of environmentally friendly wet processes in denim production, increase amount of organic cotton Updating general agreements and related supplier handbook	Good Project product sales – Preliminary Good Index Return statistics Returns are followed up with the supplier in question. Recurring cases of deficient quality or other breaches of our product requirements will entail financial consequences for our suppliers.	Production and Sustainability Manager CSR and Quality Manager
	Non-discrimination, diversity and gender equality	Gender equality, diversity and non-discrimination plan.	As a company, we seek to be a role model for equal rights and opportunities in society. Our internal efforts are part of our employer value proposition and aim to ensure we have the right skills to achieve our goals.	The Swedish Trade Confederation network. Training in psychosocial work environment topics and labour law. Salary review	Annual staff appraisals Employee surveys conducted every second year. Action plan drawn up based on results of employee survey.	HR Manager
	Occupational health and safety	Safety portal on the intranet. Safety policy, rehabilitation policy and work environment manual.	Employees in good health and spirits contribute to a profitable company, benefit society and are important from the perspective of the individual.	Preventative health and safety efforts – in stores, warehouses, logistics and the head office. Offering company healthcare services, massages and wellness allowances. Safety training, safety rounds and safety checks in stores.	Accident and incident reporting. Follow-up talks with employees.	HR Manager Security Manager
	Product responsibility	Environmental policy Supplier requirements Restricted substances list Product strategy Product safety requirement for Children's wear	We aim to ensure all products are safe to use, and meet our customers' expectations and statutory requirements.	Set product safety requirement for Children's wear. Third-party and our own quality controls in production. Visiting suppliers.	Inventory spot checks. Continuous product risk assessment, chemical and quality testing prior to production. Quality controls in production. If prohibited chemical substances/contents are discovered, the products will be stopped, if possible, before production and shipping, and they will be destroyed if no other option is possible.	CSR and Quality Manager
	Social conditions of suppliers, child labour and forced or compulsory labour	amfori Code of Conduct Bangladesh Accord Syrian Refugee Policy, Turkey UK Modern slavery act Production strategy Women's empowerment strategy	The aim is to strive for a safe and secure work environment for workers in factories that manufacture for Gina Tricot, and for suppliers to respect human rights and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.	amfori audits and our own follow-up visits. Review of audit logs outside the scope of amfori. UNICEF partnership to prevent child labour. Accord inspections.	Part of supplier evaluation and production planning where we strive to give preference to suppliers with high social standards. If suppliers violate human rights or the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, production with this supplier will be suspended immediately and a corrective action plan will be prepared. If other requirements are not met, a corrective action plan will be prepared in coordination with the supplier.	Production and Sustainability Manager CSR and Quality Manager Those responsible at the local purchasing offices

GRI INDEX

- GRI 101: Foundation 2016

GENERAL DISCLOSURES	DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
GRI 102: GENERAL DISCLOSURES 2016	102-1 Name of the organisation.	Gina Tricot AB (part of the Nordic Fashion Group)	4
	102-2 Primary brands, products and services.		4
	102-3 Location of the organisation's headquarters.		4
	102-4 Countries where the organisation operates.		4
	102-5 Ownership and legal form.	Gina Tricot is a limited company and is a part of the Nordic Fashion Group, whose principal owner is Nordic Capital. The other owners are private investors, which include Frankenius Equity AB, JA Appelqvist Holding AB and Grebbesult Holding AB.	
	102-6 Markets served.	Stores are located in Sweden (83), Denmark (15), Finland (22), Norway (35) and Germany (11). An additional 25 European countries are served by e-commerce sales.	4
	102-7 Scale of the organisation.	Number of employees 1,760 Consolidated annual sales: 2 006 172 SEK For Nordic Fashion Group AB	
	102-8 Total number of employees by employment type, gender and region.	Total number of employees: 1,760 Number of employees per country: Sweden: 849 Norway: 449 Denmark: 145 Finland: 230 Germany: 87 Bangladesh: 9 China: 10 (Consultants) Turkey: 1 (Consultant) Myanmar: 1 (Consultant) Number of employees by type of contract (permanent or temporary) per country. The numbers are approximate, we do not have a system that supports this. Sweden: Permanent: 481 Temporary: 368 Norway: 449 in total. No information on types of contract available. Denmark: Permanent: 120 Temporary: 25 Finland: Permanent: 160 Temporary: 0 Germany: Permanent: 62 Temporary: 25 Bangladesh: Permanent 10 We are unable to report the percentage of full-time and part-time employees by country or gender. A very small percentage (<2 %) of our total employees are contracted, and are therefore not directly employed by Gina Tricot. The average number of employees is reported in our annual report. All employee figures in this sustainability report are reported as at 31 December.	

DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
102-9 The organisation's supply chain.		14-18
102-10 Significant changes to the organisation's size, structure, ownership or supply chain during the reporting period.	We have a total of 170 stores, which is 5 fewer stores than the previous year. In total, we opened 4 new stores, relocated 6 stores and closed 12.	
102-11 Application of the Precautionary Principle.		32
102-12 Externally-developed economic, environmental and social charters, principles, or other initiatives to which the organisation subscribes, or which it endorses.		4, 46
102-13 Main memberships of industry or other associations, and national or international advocacy organisations.		46
<i>STRATEGY</i>		
102-14 Statement from CEO.		5
<i>ETHICS AND INTEGRITY</i>		
102-16 Values, principles, standards and norms of behaviour.	The amfori Code of Conduct is communicated to suppliers and is available in local languages. All employees are subject to our Corporate Compliance Programme and internal anticorruption guidelines. All employees undergo training in values, anti-corruption, data protection, competition legislation, trade sanctions and the whistle-blower system, which is a part of the Corporate Compliance Programme.	
<i>GOVERNANCE</i>		
102-18 Governance structure of the organisation, including committees, and committees responsible for decision-making on economic, environmental and social topics.	The board is involved in preparing on the sustainability report. The Sustainability Group reports to the board on an ongoing basis.	
<i>STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT</i>		
102-40 Stakeholder groups engaged by the organisation.		10
102-41 Percentage of total employees covered by collective bargaining agreements.	All employees in Sweden are covered by collective bargaining agreements. Other countries follow the provisions of the collective bargaining agreements.	
102-42 Basis for identifying and selecting stakeholders with whom to engage.		9
102-43 Approach to stakeholder engagement, including frequency of engagement by type and stakeholder group.		10
102-44 Key topics and concerns that have been raised through stakeholder engagement, including how the organisation has responded to those key topics and concerns.		10

DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
<i>REPORTING PRACTICE</i>		
102-45 Entities included in the consolidated financial statements and whether any of them are not covered by the sustainability report.	This sustainability report covers Gina Tricot AB and the sales companies in each of the 5 countries where we have stores. Our financial reporting and employee information also cover Nordic Fashion Group AB.	
102-46 The process for defining the report content and the topic Boundaries.		12
102-47 Material topics identified in the process for defining report content.		12, 47-48
102-48 The effect of any restatements of information given in previous reports, and the reasons for such restatements.	Any restatements of information are always reported in connection with the reported indicators. No other information has been changed in comparison to previous reports.	
102-49 Significant changes from previous reporting periods in the list of material topics and topic Boundaries.	No significant changes have been made.	
102-50 Reporting period.	The reporting period is the 2019 fiscal year.	
102-51 Publication date of the most recent previous report.	April 2019	
102-52 Reporting cycle.	Annual	
102-53 Contact point for questions regarding the report or its contents.	Rebecca Watkins, CSR and Quality Manager, rebecca.watkins@ginatricot.com	
102-54 Choice of reporting option.	This report has been prepared in accordance with the GRI Standards: Core option.	
102-55 GRI Index.		49-55
102-56 External assurance.	This report has not been externally assured.	

MATERIAL TOPICS	DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
<i>ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	Our financial performance is clearly limited to our business, in accordance with financial reporting and accounting rules. Several entities are in turn affected by our financial performance, such as our suppliers who require payment for products and services they deliver, employees who expect salaries for work performed and our owners who seek a return on their investment.	
	103-2, 103-3 Description and evaluation of the management approach.		47
GRI 201: Economic Performance 2016	201-1 Direct economic value generated and distributed.	Value (in SEK million) Net sales: 2006 (2,022) Operating costs: -1,500 (-1,567) Employee wages and benefits: -338 (-383) Interest: -6 (-7) Taxes: -85 (-101) Community investments: -4 (0) Economic value retained: 73 (-35) Liabilities: -1,178 (-592) Equity: -431 (-364) Sold products (number of items): 14,568,158 (14,806,907) The figures above are consolidated figures for Nordic Fashion Group AB	
<i>ANTI-CORRUPTION</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.		27, 47
	103-2, 103-3 Description and evaluation of the management approach.		27, 47
GRI 205: Anti-corruption 2016	205-2 The percentage of employees who have received training on the organisation's anti-corruption policies and procedures.		27
	205-3 Confirmed incidents of corruption and actions taken.		27
<i>MATERIALS</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.		29-31
	103-2, 103-3 Description and evaluation of the management approach.		29-31, 48
Other disclosure	Own indicator: List of more sustainable materials. Total % of garments produced using more sustainable materials.		29
<i>ENERGY</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.		38
	103-2, 103-3 Description and evaluation of the management approach.		38, 47
GRI 302: Energy 2016	302-1 Energy consumption within the organisation.		39

MATERIAL TOPICS	DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
<i>EMISSIONS</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	38-39, 43
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	38, 43, 47
GRI 305: Emissions 2016	305-1	Total direct green house gas emmissions (Scope 1)	39
	305-2	Total indirect greenhouse gas emissions (Scope 2).	39, 43
	305-3	Other relevant indirect greenhouse gas emissions (Scope 3).	
<i>ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF SUPPLIERS</i>			30, 33, 38, 40
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	15, 29-31, 33, 40, 47
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	29-31, 33, 40, 47
GRI 308: Supplier Environmental Assessment 2016	308-2	Negative environmental impacts in the supply chain and actions taken.	
<i>OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY</i>			26-27
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	26-27,48
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	27
GRI 403: Occupational Health and Safety 2016	403-2	Types of injury and rates of injury, occupational diseases, lost days, absenteeism, and number of work-related fatalities.	
<i>DIVERSITY AND EQUAL OPPORTUNITY</i>			26
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary. Diversity, equal opportunity and non-discrimination are linked clearly together in our efforts.	48
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach. Number of employees in each age group.	27
GRI 405: Diversity and Equal Opportunity 2016	405-1	Diversity reported for senior executives and other staff.	

MATERIAL TOPICS	DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
<i>NON-DISCRIMINATION</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	26
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	26, 48
GRI 406: Non-discrimination 2016	406-1	Incidents of discrimination and corrective actions taken.	26
<i>CHILD LABOUR</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	23, 45
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	15-16, 23, 48
GRI 408: Child Labor 2016	408-1	Operations and suppliers considered to have significant risk for incidents of child labour, and measures taken intended to contribute to the effective abolition of child labour.	23-25, 45, 48
<i>FORCED OR COMPULSORY LABOUR</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	16, 18, 45
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	15-16, 18, 48
GRI 409: Forced or Compulsory Labor 2016	409-1	Operations and suppliers considered to have significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour, and measures taken intended to contribute to the elimination of all forms of forced or compulsory labour.	16, 18, 45
<i>SOCIAL CONDITIONS IN OUR SUPPLY CHAIN</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	16-20
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	15-19, 48
GRI 414: Supplier Social Assessment 2016	414-1	Percentage of new suppliers that were screened using social criteria.	15
	414-2	Negative social impacts in the supply chain and actions taken.	16-20, 23
<i>PRODUCT RESPONSIBILITY</i>			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1	Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.	32
	103-2, 103-3	Description and evaluation of the management approach.	32, 48
GRI 416: Customer Health and Safety 2016	416-1	Percentage of significant product and service categories for which health and safety impacts are assessed for improvement.	32

MATERIAL TOPICS	DISCLOSURES	COMMENTS AND OMISSIONS MADE	PAGE
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ANIMAL WELFARE ISSUES

GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundary.		31
	103-2, 103-3 Description and evaluation of the management approach.		31, 47
<i>Other disclosures</i>	Indicator not available, reporting only refers to management disclosures		

Auditor's report on the statutory sustainability report

To the general meeting of the shareholders in Gina Tricot AB, corporate identity number 556534-8843

Engagement and responsibility

The board of directors is responsible for the statutory sustainability report for the year 2019 and for ensuring that it has been prepared in accordance with the Annual Accounts Act.

The scope of the audit

Our examination has been conducted in accordance with FAR's auditing standard RevR 12, The auditor's opinion regarding the statutory sustainability report. This means that our examination of the statutory sustainability report is substantially different and less in scope than an audit conducted in accordance with International Standards on Auditing and generally accepted auditing standards in Sweden. We believe that the examination has provided us with sufficient basis for our opinion.

Opinion

A statutory sustainability report has been prepared.

Gothenburg, 28th of April 2020
Öhrlings PricewaterhouseCoopers AB

Fredrik Göransson

Authorised Public Accountant

This sustainability report is issued by the Board of Directors of Gina Tricot, corporate identity number 556534-8843:**Directors**

Paul Frankenius
Fabian Månsson
Emilia se Poret
Felix Kreyer
David Samuelsson
Victor Appelqvist
Morten Faye Eriksen

Deputies

Annette Appelqvist

Approved by the board of directors, 28th of April 2020.

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